

Human stress detection with wearable sensors using convolutional neural networks

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we propose and evaluate a deep learning architecture based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for human stress detection using wearable sensors. This architecture has a first part that includes three convolutional layers for learning features from several biosignals. The second part is composed of three fully connected layers for stress detection. Additionally, we analyze several biosignal processing techniques to be applied before defining the inputs to the deep learning architecture: Fourier transform, cube root and Constant Q Transform (CQT). This analysis was performed with a public dataset, Wearable Stress and Affect Detection dataset (recorded by Robert Bosch GmbH Corporate Research, Germany), using a leave-one-subject-out cross validation. We evaluated three different classification tasks including different emotional states. The accuracy increased from 93.1% to 96.6% when classifying stress vs. non-stress states, from 80.3% to 85.1% for differencing baseline vs. stress vs. amusement, and from 77.1% to 82.1% when discriminating five classes: baseline, stress, amusement, meditation and recovery.

Keywords:

Human stress detection; Inertial signals; Physiological signals; Convolutional Neural Networks; Fourier Transform; Cube Root; Constant Q Transform.

1. Introduction

Stress can be considered as a mental state that provokes physical or mental tension. In aviation industry, there are many professionals with high level of stress at work like pilots or air traffic controllers. An excess of stress level can eventually focus his or her attention too much, reducing the awareness of other aspects. This situation can increase the risk of human errors [1]. Additionally, This factor has been associated to the development of several illness like obesity [2], diabetes [3], asthma [4] or cardiovascular diseases [5].

Stress produces physiological responses generating characteristic patterns in some biosignals like skin conductance, heart rate or body temperature [6][7]. Stress detection can be done by using signal processing

27 and machine learning techniques to identify characteristic patterns in these biosignals. Automatic stress
28 monitoring has important benefits. First, automatic detection can help people to manage stress situations
29 reducing the effect on their work, health or daily activities [8], like driving [9][10]. Moreover, physicians
30 could have objective metrics to evaluate the stress exposure of the patients or to develop intelligent medical
31 applications that adapt their behavior to the level of stress (i.e. blood glucose predictor for diabetic patients).

32 The fast development of wearable technologies and the wide expansion of smart devices have
33 facilitated the recording of biosignals during daily activities [11]. These technologies have permitted the
34 design and implementation of low-cost stress supervision systems based on wearable sensors. This paper
35 contributes proposing and evaluating a stress detection system based on deep learning using wearable
36 sensors. The main contributions can be detailed in the following points:

- 37 • Firstly, we propose and evaluate a deep learning architecture based on Convolutional Neural Networks
38 (CNNs) for stress monitoring. This architecture has a first part that includes three convolutional layers
39 for extracting features from inertial and physiological signals. The second part is composed of three
40 fully connected layers for stress detection.
- 41 • Secondly, we analyze several signal processing techniques to be applied before defining the inputs to
42 the deep learning architecture: Fourier transform, cube root and Constant Q Transform (CQT).

43 These contributions were evaluated with a public dataset, WESAD (Wearable Stress and Affect
44 Detection)[12], recorded by Robert Bosch GmbH Corporate Research in Germany. This evaluation was
45 performed using a leave-one-subject-out (LOSO) cross validation. This analysis allows estimating the system
46 performance when monitoring subjects not considered in the training set. This paper analyses the different
47 contributions in three classification tasks with two classes (stress vs. non-stress), three classes (stress vs.
48 baseline vs, amusement) and five classes (stress vs. baseline vs, amusement vs. meditation vs. recovery).
49 These classification tasks were also addressed in previous works [12][13]. This paper reports the best results
50 on these tasks using a LOSO cross-validation.

51 This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 includes related work on stress detection. Section 3
52 describes the material and methods used in this study: the dataset and signal processing and deep learning

53 modules. The experiments and the obtained results are detailed in section 4. Finally, section 5 summarizes
54 the main conclusions of the paper.

55 **2. Related work on stress detection using biosignals**

56 This section reviews related work in stress detection using biosignals. Many previous works focused
57 on extracting handcrafted features from physiological signals like electroencephalograph (EEG) [14],
58 electrocardiogram (ECG), electromyogram (EMG) and electrodermal activity (EDA), and physical signals
59 like respiration, temperature or eye activity. The review provided by Giannakakis et al. [15] describes a
60 summary of the main characteristics obtained from these biosignals.

61 Features obtained from ECGs include metrics obtained from QRS curves, heart rate, heart rate
62 variability or energy distribution in the frequency domain [16][17][18][19][20][21][22]. ECG and EDA are
63 the biosignals most frequently used for stress monitoring. EDA has two main components: skin conductance
64 level (SCL) and skin conductance response (SCR). SCL shows the slow variation and SCR the short-term
65 reaction to some stimulus. Main EDA features are extracted from SCR curves [23][24][25][26]: number of
66 peaks, peak duration, peak value, slope, etc. Regarding EMG most of the features are extracted from the
67 energy distribution in a wide range of frequency reaching several hundreds of Hz [27].

68 These physiological signals can be complemented with physical signals like respiration [16][29][28]
69 or body temperature [21]. In both cases, main features are obtained from simple statistics along a certain
70 time. In the case of the respiration, the relation between inspiration and expiration time can also provide
71 stress information [29].

72 Thanks to the fast expanding of wearable devices, new datasets including a high number of biosignals
73 have become available to the research community: SWELL [30], Multimodal Stress Detection [31], WESAD
74 [12] in an academic environment [32]. When combining several biosignals for stress detection, machine
75 learning algorithms can help to deal with a more complex task of finding stress patterns in a multimodal
76 scenario. In the literature, there are several previous works that analyzed and compared several machine
77 learning algorithms [12][13][17][25][32], including Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, Decision
78 Trees, Regression Strategies, Boost algorithms, K-Nearest Neighbors, etc. The best results were obtained
79 with the combination of several of these algorithms. Some references include interesting comparison tables

80 including relevant characteristics of each work [26][32]: signals, features and machine learning algorithms
81 and performance.

82 The application of deep learning algorithms is increasing very fast due the better performance reached
83 with these techniques. Deep neural networks can be used to detect stress pattern but also, they can be used to
84 learn and combine relevant features from several biosignals. In the literature, there are studies on stress
85 detection that used deep learning algorithms for classifying handcrafted features [19][13]. Other studies used
86 recurrent neural networks (RNNs) to learn features and classify stress patterns from ECGs [16] or ECG in
87 combination with car driving signals [34]. In this work, we propose a deep learning architecture based on
88 CNNs to learn relevant features from a high number of biosignals (14 biosignals) and detect stress patterns.
89 We also study several alternatives for processing the signals before being considered as inputs to the CNNs.

90 Regarding the system architecture for pervasive healthcare applications, previous works have focused
91 on analyze the evolution of information and communication technology for the improvement of quality of
92 life [35]. In fact, some works have identified the most representative healthcare scenarios that can benefit
93 from 5G networks [36] and they have proposed cascaded networks to handle healthcare traffic in assisted-
94 living applications for chronic patients [37]. The architecture of this work is based on computing different
95 signal processing techniques for each type of signal and feed a CNN with multi-modal sensed data.
96 Afterwards, this CNN architecture combines this information and learn dependencies among the different
97 signals to perform the classification task.

98 The proposed architecture was evaluated with the WESAD dataset using a LOSO cross-validation,
99 similar to Schmidt et al.'s and Chakraborty et al.'s previous works [12] [13]. Schmidt et al. [12] used
100 handcrafted features for each biosignal, evaluating several machine learning algorithms. They reported
101 results on two classification tasks: stress vs. non-stress and baseline vs. stress vs. amusement. Chakraborty et
102 al. [13] used a deep neural network to detect stress patterns from handcrafted features. They evaluated their
103 proposal on a classification task considering five classes: baseline, stress, amusement, meditation and
104 recovery. The results presented in this paper improved results reported in these two previous works on this
105 dataset.

106 3. Material and methods

107 The stress detection system developed in this work consists of three main modules: the first one
108 collects the inertial and physiological signals from different devices, the second one processes these multi-
109 modal data to define the best inputs to the deep neural network, and the third module includes the deep
110 neural network that extracts the main features and detect stress periods. Figure 1 shows the general
111 architecture of the stress detection system. In this section, we comment the dataset, the signal processing
112 methods analyzed in this paper and the deep learning structure considered for stress detection.

113

Figure 1. General architecture of the stress detection system.

114 3.1. Dataset description

115 In this study, we used a public dataset, WESAD (Wearable Stress and Affect Detection) [12]. This
116 dataset includes recordings from 15 subjects (12 male and 3 female) wearing two wearable devices: a
117 RespiBAN Professional and Empatica E4. The RespiBAN device, on the chest, recorded body acceleration
118 (in three axes), body temperature, respiration, electrocardiogram (ECG), electromyogram (EMG) and
119 electrodermal activity (EDA). All these signals were sampled at 700 Hz. The Empatica E4 bracelet (on the
120 wrist) measured hand acceleration (in three axes), arm temperature, blood volume pulse (BVP) and
121 electrodermal activity (EDA). These signals were recorded with different sampling frequencies but all of
122 them were upsampled to 64 Hz using the Fourier method. The evaluation subjects were selected excluding
123 people with mental or cardiovascular problems, pregnant people or heavy smokers. The mean age was 27.5.

124 After synchronizing and instating all the devices in the subject's body, all the subjects followed a
125 protocol in a laboratory considering several phases:

- 126 • Baseline phase: the subject was asked to remain in a neutral position at a table (sitting or standing)
127 reading some magazines for 20 minutes.

- 128 • Amusement phase: the participant watched funny videos with a duration of 6 minutes.
- 129 • Stress phase: the stress phase was provoked by exposing the subjects to a Trier Social Stress Test
- 130 (TSST) [38] for 10 minutes. This test consisted of a public speaking and a mental arithmetic task. First,
- 131 each subject was asked to speak about their personal strengths and weaknesses in front of human
- 132 resources people, and second, each participant was asked to subtract 17 from 2,023 to zero without
- 133 errors.
- 134 • Meditation phase: the subjects were guided by an expert to perform breathing exercises with closed
- 135 eyes while sitting in a comfortable position to re-establish them to neural affective mood.
- 136 • Recovery phase: both devices were synchronized again and removed from subject's body.

137 Regarding the specific postures of the subjects while the data collection protocol, the baseline,

138 amusement, and stress phases were conducted either standing or sitting (half of the subjects were standing

139 and half were sitting for each phase). During the meditation phase, all subjects were sitting.

140 Considering previous works on stress monitoring [12] [13] using this dataset, three different

141 classification tasks have been considered. These are the classification tasks analyzed in this work:

- 142 • In the first classification task [12], only data from three phases were considered: baseline, stress and
- 143 amusement phases. The target was to detect stress (stress phase) from non-stress (baseline and
- 144 amusement phases) (S vs. NS).
- 145 • The second classification task [12] consisted of distinguishing between baseline, stress, and amusement
- 146 phases (B vs. S vs. A).
- 147 • Finally, the third task [13] focused on discriminating between 5 classes: baseline, stress, amusement,
- 148 meditation, and recovery phases (B vs. S vs. A vs. M vs. R).

149 **3.2. Signal processing**

150 All signals from wearable devices (RespiBAN on the chest and Empatica E4 on the wrist) were

151 segmented in 60-second windows with a shift of 0.25 seconds. The classification is performed at the window

152 level. Previous works [12] [13] used the same windowing, extracting handcrafted features from each window

153 to be passed to the classifier. In this work, we did not extract handcrafted features, but we processed the

154 different signals before passing them to the CNN. The convolutional layers in the CNN were responsible of
155 learning appropriate features for stress detection.

156 For all signals, we subdivided each 60-second window into **P-second sub-windows** with a shift of 0.25
157 seconds. We computed the Fourier transform (using the Fast Fourier Transform, FFT) and obtained the
158 spectrum (module of the Fourier transform) of each sub-window, and then we averaged the spectrum along
159 all the sub-windows in a 60-second window. Finally, we selected a frequency range of the average spectrum
160 and the spectrum coefficients included in this range were the inputs to the CNN.

161 We computed different processing techniques depending on each signal to accommodate the
162 heterogeneous signals and feed the CNN. These signals had different sampling frequency and contained
163 relevant information within a specific frequency range. For these reasons, each 60-second window was
164 subdivided into **P-second sub-windows** in such a way that the number of points **M** was equal to 210. This
165 number of points was obtained by multiplying the sub-window length by the upper bound of frequency range
166 in each signal. This computation allowed stacking all inputs in a $N \times M$ matrix, where **N** is the number of
167 signals of each window and **M** the number of points of each signal (210 in our case). For example, for the
168 RespiBAN accelerometer, each 60-second window of three accelerations (in X, Y and Z axes) were
169 subdivided in 7-second sub-windows shifted 0.25 seconds. The frequency range in these cases was 0-30 Hz,
170 the motion information above 30Hz is negligible. For 7-second sub-windows, we obtained a spectrum with a
171 resolution of seven points per Hz. Considering a range of 0-30 Hz, we obtained 210 spectral points as inputs
172 to the CNN. Figure 2 shows the signal processing steps for this example, where a 60-second window is
173 subdivided into 7-second sub-windows and the FFT is computed for each sub-window within the range 0-30
174 Hz. Afterwards, the average spectrum is computed to obtain the spectrum of the 60-second window, which is
175 represented by 210 points. Table 1 summarizes all the details per signal. In all cases, the number of inputs to
176 the CNN is the same, 210.

177

Figure 2. Signal processing steps for RespiBAN accelerometer signals.

Table 1 : Processing details per signal.

Device	Signal	Sampling frequency	Frequency range	Sub-window length	Number of inputs to CNN
RespiBAN (Chest)	Accelerations (X, Y and Z)	700 Hz	0 - 30 Hz	7 seconds	210
	ECG	700 Hz	0 - 7 Hz	30 seconds	210
	EDA	700 Hz	0 - 7 Hz	30 seconds	210
	EMG	700 Hz	0 - 250 Hz	0.84 seconds	210
	RESP	700 Hz	0 - 6 Hz	35 seconds	210
	TEMP	700 Hz	0 - 6 Hz	35 seconds	210
Empatica E4 (Wrist)	Accelerations (X, Y and Z)	64 Hz	0 - 30 Hz	7 seconds	210
	BVP	64 Hz	0 - 7 Hz	30 seconds	210
	EDA	64 Hz	0 - 7 Hz	30 seconds	210
	TEMP	64 Hz	0 - 6 Hz	35 seconds	210

178

179 The first variant we considered was to calculate the cube root (CR) of sub-window spectrums before
 180 averaging in a 60-second window. The cube root allows emphasizing harmonics with low energy
 181 remarking the spectral information.

182 The second variant consisted in computing Constant Q Transform (CQT) [39] in sub-windows. This
 183 CQT was implemented as a postprocessing step after Fourier transform, as suggested by Brown et al
 184 [40]. CQT transforms a time-domain signal into a frequency representation where the frequency bins are
 185 geometrically spaced with equal Q-factors. The Q factor is the ratio of the center frequency and the

186 bandwidth. CQT provides more resolution at low frequencies and defines the same distance between
187 consecutive harmonics, independently of the fundamental frequency. Maintaining the same distance
188 between consecutive harmonics facilitates the learning process of convolutional filters in the CNN. In
189 this work, we have considered 21 bins for postprocessing the 210 frequency points obtained after Fourier
190 transform and frequency range selection. F represents the frequency filters used to obtain the 21 CQT
191 bins. We applied the same frequency filters to postprocess the 210 points of all signals. As the selected
192 210 points corresponded to different frequency ranges, the CQT is automatically adapted to the
193 frequency range of each signal. After CQT application, the number of inputs to the CNN per signal was
194 reduced from 210 to 21.

195
196 *Figure 3. CQT filters for postprocessing Fourier transform.*

197 **3.3. Convolutional neural networks**

198 Figure 4 represents the CNN used in this work. Table 2 summaries settings for all the layers. The first
199 part of the CNN learns relevant features from signals spectra. This part is composed of three convolutional
200 layers with two intermediate maxpooling layers. With the target of not increasing a lot the number of
201 parameters, we considered kernel sizes of (1 x 3) in all convolutional layers. For simplicity, the padding
202 characteristic was defined as ‘same’: input and output shapes are the same.

203 The classification part includes three fully connected layers for classification, with a decreasing
 204 number of units. In order to avoid overfitting, we included dropout layers (with a fraction of 0.3) after
 205 convolutional and fully connected layers. ReLU is the activation function in intermediate layers reducing the
 206 impact of gradient vanishing effect.

207

Figure 4. Deep learning structure including convolutional and fully connected layers.

Table 2 : Configuration details and number of parameters to train for all the layers considering an input with shape $N=14 \times M=210$.

Layer	Output shape	Param #	Activation function	Other characteristics
Input	(-, 14, 210, 1)	-	-	-
Feature extraction				
2D Conv	(-, 14, 210, 64)	256	ReLU	# Kernels = 64, Size = 1 x 3, Stride = 1, Padding = 'same'
Dropout	(-, 14, 210, 64)	-	-	portion = 0.3
2D Conv	(-, 14, 210, 64)	12352	ReLU	# Kernels = 64, Size = 1 x 3 x 64, Stride = 1, Padding = 'same'
2D Max Pooling	(-, 14, 105, 64)	-	-	Pool size = 1 x 2
Dropout	(-, 14, 105, 64)	-	-	portion = 0.3
2D Conv	(-, 1, 105, 64)	12352	ReLU	# Kernels = 64, Size = 1 x 3 x 64, Stride = 1, Padding = 'same'
Dropout	(-, 1, 105, 64)	-	-	portion = 0.3
2D Max Pooling	(-, 1, 52, 64)	-	-	Pool size = 1 x 2
Dropout	(-, 1, 52, 64)	-	-	portion = 0.3
Classification				
Flatten	(-, 46592)	-	-	
Dense	(-, 128)	5963904	ReLU	# Neurons = 128, Initializer='glorot_uniform'
Dropout	(-, 128)	-	-	portion = 0.3
Dense	(-, 64)	8256	ReLU	# Neurons = 64, Initializer='glorot_uniform'
Dropout	(-, 64)	-	-	portion = 0.3
Dense	(-, P)	65 x P	Softmax	# Neurons = P, Initializer='glorot_uniform'
Output	(-, P)	-	-	-

208

209 The CNN input is a 2 D matrix $N \times M$, where N is the number of signals and M the number of points
210 per signal. N varies depending on the number of signals considered in the experiment and M is different if
211 we consider Fourier transform (210 points) of the CQT (21 points). The number of outputs correspond to the
212 number of classes considered in the classification problem, using the softmax function and the categorical
213 cross-entropy loss metric.

214 We used the training set (using part of the training set for validation) to tune number of epochs (10)
215 and `batch_size` (50). The optimizer was fixed to the root-mean-square propagation method [41].

216 4. Results

217 The experimental setup is the same than in previous works [12] [13], we used a LOSO cross validation
218 along the 15 subjects: 14 subjects were used for training and 1 for testing. This process was repeated 15
219 times leaving a different subject for testing every time.

220 For evaluating the results, we considered accuracy and F1-score in percentages. The accuracy is the
221 ratio between the number of correctly classified examples and the number of total samples. The F1-score is
222 the harmonic mean of precision and recall. The final F1-score is the average along the classes. All the
223 analyses were performed in the three classification tasks addressed in this paper (see section 3.1). Both
224 evaluation metrics include confidence intervals (of 95%), obtained with the next equation [42]. ACC is the
225 accuracy in percentage and N the number of examples (60-second windows) used in the evaluation. Two
226 experiments are significantly different when there is not overlap in the confidence intervals computed with
227 the following equation. N is the number of examples used in the test and ACC is the performing metric
228 (Accuracy or F1-score) in percentage

$$CI (95\%) = \pm 1.96 \sqrt{\frac{ACC \cdot (100 - ACC)}{N}} \quad (1)$$

229
230 The main parameters of the deep learning structure were adjusted subdividing the training set into
231 training (13 subjects) and validation (1 subject) sets. Thirteen subjects were used for weights training while

232 the validation subject was used for tuning the hyperparameters of the CNN. Once the CNN structure was
 233 defined, the weights were retrained using the 14 subjects.

234 4.1. Signal processing analysis

235 Table 3 compares the performance obtained for the three classification tasks depending on the signal
 236 processing strategy. These results were obtained using all signals recorded from RaspiBAN and Empatica E4
 237 devices. The first conclusion is that applying the cube root over the Fourier spectrum improved significantly
 238 the results. As commented before, the cube root allowed emphasizing frequencies with low energy
 239 remarking the harmonic structure. The CQT did not provide any additional improvement but we obtained the
 240 same performance (high overlap in the confidence intervals) reducing significantly (10 times) the input
 241 shape: from 14 x 210 without CQT to 14 x 21 with CQT. In order to reduce the CNN input shape, we apply
 242 CQT in the next experiments.

Table 3 : Accuracy (%) and F1-score (%) depending on the signal processing module considering all signals in the three classifications tasks.

Signal processing	S vs. NS		B vs. S vs. A		B vs. S vs. A vs. M vs. R	
	Accuracy	F1-score	Accuracy	F1-score	Accuracy	F1-score
Fourier Transform	95.20 ± 0.13	95.13 ± 0.13	83.12 ± 0.13	82.67 ± 0.13	79.67 ± 0.25	79.24 ± 0.25
Fourier + Cube Root	96.73 ± 0.11	96.65 ± 0.11	85.00 ± 0.11	84.92 ± 0.22	81.21 ± 0.24	81.45 ± 0.24
Fourier + Cube Root + CQT	96.62 ± 0.11	96.63 ± 0.11	85.03 ± 0.22	85.01 ± 0.22	81.15 ± 0.24	81.70 ± 0.24

243 4.2. Comparison with previous studies

244 In this section, we compare the performance of the proposed system with previous results reported in
 245 the literature. This comparison is done for the three classification tasks addressed in this work and detailing
 246 the results for different groups of signals. We grouped signals recorded on the chest (RaspiBAN device) into
 247 inertial signals (accelerations in three axes) and physiological signals (ECG, EDA, EMG, temperature and
 248 respiration). In a similar way, signals from the wrist (Empatica E4) were divided into inertial signals
 249 (accelerations in the three axes) and physiological signals (BVP, EDA and temperature).

250 Table 4 compares our results with those obtained by Schmidt et al. [12] for the 2-class classification
 251 problem (stress vs. non-stress), considering different groups of signals. Our results were significantly better

252 than those obtained by Schmidt et al. for all groups of signals. In both studies, physiological signals from the
 253 chest was the best group of signals while the inertial signals from the wrist was the worst. It is important to
 254 note how the CNN can integrate information from different devices and types of signals obtaining an
 255 important improvement when using all signals.

Table 4 : Accuracy (%) and F1-score (%) comparison with Schmidt et al. [12] classifying between stress and non-stress situations.

Stress vs. Non-stress				
	Schmidt et al. [12]		This paper	
	Accuracy	F1-score	Accuracy	F1-score
Chest inertial signals (acc)	73.87	62.12	90.60 ± 0.18	90.50 ± 0.18
Chest physiological signals	93.12	91.47	93.20 ± 0.16	92.70 ± 0.16
Wrist inertial signals (acc)	71.69	61.70	88.70 ± 0.20	88.50 ± 0.20
Wrist physiological signals	88.33	86.10	87.30 ± 0.21	87.00 ± 0.21
All inertial signals (acc)	-	-	91.50 ± 0.17	91.30 ± 0.17
All physiological signals	92.51	90.93	95.01 ± 0.13	94.78 ± 0.13
All chest signals	92.83	91.07	93.10 ± 0.16	93.01 ± 0.16
All wrist signals	87.12	84.11	92.70 ± 0.16	92.55 ± 0.16
All signals	92.28	90.74	96.62 ± 0.11	96.63 ± 0.11

256

257 Table 5 shows the confusion matrix for the case of using all signals to classify between stress and non-
 258 stress windows. The accuracy is very high for both classes.

Table 5 : Confusion matrix considering all signals for classifying between stress and non-stress situations.

		Prediction	
		Non-stress	Stress
Ground Truth	Non-stress	96.5%	3.5%
	Stress	3.2%	96.8%

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260 Table 6 shows the same comparison considering the 3-class classification task (baseline, stress and
 261 amusement). Our results were significantly better than those obtained by Schmidt et al. [12] for all groups of
 262 signals. In this case, the physiological signals provided the best results, similar to those reported when
 263 combining all signals. Accelerations did not provide any help in this task.

Table 6 : Accuracy (%) and F1-score (%) comparison with Schmidt et al. [12] classifying between baseline, stress and amusement situations.

Baseline vs. Stress vs. Amusement				
	Schmidt et al. [12]		This paper	
	Accuracy	F1-score	Accuracy	F1-score
Chest inertial signals (acc)	56.56	44.28	68.32 ± 0.29	69.86 ± 0.29

Chest physiological signals	80.34	72.51	81.87 ± 0.24	81.21 ± 0.24
Wrist inertial signals (acc)	57.20	46.38	71.82 ± 0.28	71.23 ± 0.28
Wrist physiological signals	76.17	66.33	75.10 ± 0.27	74.00 ± 0.27
All inertial signals (acc)	-	-	72.23 ± 0.28	72.90 ± 0.28
All physiological signals	79.86	71.10	85.10 ± 0.22	85.05 ± 0.22
All chest signals	76.50	72.49	77.11 ± 0.26	76.90 ± 0.26
All wrist signals	75.21	64.12	74.90 ± 0.27	74.60 ± 0.27
All signals	79.57	68.85	85.03 ± 0.22	85.01 ± 0.22

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Table 7 shows the confusion matrix for the case of using all signals to classify between baseline, stress and amusement. The accuracy is very high when detecting stress, but this accuracy decreases very much for amusement showing an important confusion between amusement and baseline.

Table 7 : Confusion matrix considering all signals for classifying between baseline, stress and amusement situations.

		Prediction		
		Baseline	Stress	Amusement
Ground Truth	Baseline	85.0%	2.5%	12.5%
	Stress	0.7%	98.3%	1.0%
	Amusement	25.8%	8.0%	66.2%

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Table 8 shows the results for the 5-class classification task and compares them with those reported by Chakraborty et al. [13]. Our results demonstrate the better performance of the system proposed in this paper. Similar to the previous analysis, the physiological signals provided the best results, obtaining the same results than when combining all signals. Accelerations did not provide any additional improvement. In Chakraborty et al. [13], authors used a deep learning structure, but the main difference was in the CNN input. While Chakraborty et al. extracted handcrafted features to feed the CNN, we used enhanced spectra as CNN inputs, leaving the CNN to learn specific features from those spectra.

Table 8 : Accuracy (%) and F1-score (%) comparison with Chakraborty et al. [13] classifying between baseline, stress, amusement, meditation and recovery situations.

	Baseline vs. Stress vs. Amusement vs. Meditation vs. Recovery			
	Chakraborty et al. [13]		This paper	
	Accuracy	F1-score	Accuracy	F1-score
Chest inertial signals (acc)	-	-	54.91 ± 0.31	53.71 ± 0.31
Chest physiological signals	-	-	76.67 ± 0.26	75.23 ± 0.26
Wrist inertial signals (acc)	-	-	58.05 ± 0.31	57.12 ± 0.31
Wrist physiological signals	-	-	61.23 ± 0.30	62.34 ± 0.30
All inertial signals (acc)	-	-	59.78 ± 0.30	60.37 ± 0.30
All physiological signals	-	-	82.12 ± 0.24	81.64 ± 0.24

All chest signals	-	-	77.21 ± 0.26	77.67 ± 0.26
All wrist signals	-	-	70.02 ± 0.28	70.23 ± 0.28
All signals	77.06	78.24	81.15 ± 0.24	81.70 ± 0.24

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277 Table 9 shows the confusion matrix for the case of using all signals to classify between baseline,
 278 stress, amusement, meditation and recovery. The accuracy is very high when detecting stress. This accuracy
 279 is small for amusement and recovery, showing an important confusion between baseline, amusement and
 280 recovery.

Table 9 : Confusion matrix considering all signals for classifying between baseline, stress, amusement, meditation and recovery situations.

		Prediction				
		Baseline	Stress	Amusement	Meditation	Recovery
Ground Truth	Baseline	78.0%	1.9%	13.5%	2.5%	4.1%
	Stress	0.8%	96.7%	1.0%	1.0%	0.5%
	Amusement	23.3%	1.4%	48.8%	16.5%	10.0%
	Meditation	2.5%	0.5%	5.0%	90.5%	1.5%
	Recovery	13.0%	1.0%	19.0%	8.5%	58.5%

281 4.3. Analysis of the window length

282 All the results reported in previous sections were obtained using a 60-second window. This
 283 characteristic allowed the comparison with previous works on this dataset. In order to extend the analysis, we
 284 studied the influence of the window length in the three classification tasks (Figure 5). In these experiments,
 285 all the signals from both devices were considered to detect stress.

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Figure 5. Accuracy evolution depending on the window length for the three classification tasks. All signals were considered for classification.

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The performance obtained with 60-second windows was improved (over 1%) increasing the analysis window to 90 seconds. On the one hand, we reached saturation in accuracy with longer windows. On the other hand, reducing to half the window length, the performance decreased significantly.

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5. Conclusions

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Automatic stress detection from biosignals is very important to evaluate stress situations and report objective metrics to physicians. These metrics can be very interesting to evaluate the stress exposure of the patients between consecutive visits. The main contributions of this paper are the proposal of a deep learning architecture based on CNNs for stress detection, and the analysis of several signal processing techniques to generate the inputs to the deep learning architecture: Fourier transform, cube root and Constant Q Transform (CQT). The CNN learn features and detect stress patterns from several biosignals in parallel.

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Regarding the signal processing techniques, the main conclusion is that the cube root over the Fourier spectrum improved significantly the results. The cube root emphasized frequencies with low energy making the harmonic structure more apparent. Although, the CQT did not provide any additional improvement, we were to reduce 10 times the input shape to the CNN.

302 These analyses were performed with a public dataset, Wearable Stress and Affect Detection dataset,
303 using a leave-one-subject-out cross validation. We evaluated the contributions in three different
304 classifications tasks. Comparing the obtained results with previous works [12] [13], the accuracy increased
305 from 93.1% to 96.6% classifying stress vs. non-stress states. For the task of differencing between baseline vs.
306 stress vs. amusement, the accuracy increased from 80.3% to 85.1%. In this classification task, the highest
307 confusion appeared between non-stress states (baseline and amusement). Finally, comparing our results with
308 those presented by Chakraborty et al. [13], the accuracy increased from 77.1% to 82.1% when dealing with
309 five classes: baseline, stress, amusement, meditation and recovery. The highest accuracy is obtained when
310 detecting stress and the lowest when discriminating between baseline, amusement and recovery.

311 **Conflict of interest**

312 Authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

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